

ν 's from Cosmology

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Planck

WMAP

ACT

SPT

DES

BOSS/SDSS

KIDS/VLT

JWST

HST

DESI

SUPPORTED BY FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH COUNCIL (ERC) UNDER THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON-ERC-2022 (GRANT AGREEMENT NO. 101076865)

NuPhys 26
King's College, London
January 09th, 2026

Schematic view of ν through the universe

- Before 1 MeV: ν interact efficiently through the **weak interaction**. They form a **perfect thermalized fluid**.
- After 1 MeV: The weak interaction drops below Hubble. They form a **free-streaming “frozen” fluid**.

The cosmic ν -background

- ν carry a **frozen Fermi-Dirac** distribution

$$f_\nu(E_\nu, t) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(p/T_\nu)}$$

does not depend on m_ν !

- ν are **slightly colder than CMB**: they decouple before e^\pm annihilations

$$T_\nu = \left(\frac{4}{11}\right)^{1/3} T_\gamma$$

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$$T_\nu = \left(\frac{4}{11}\right)^{1/3} T_\gamma$$

- N_{eff} parametrizes the **number of massless ν -like species**

$$\rho_R = \rho_\gamma \left(1 + \frac{7}{8} \left(\frac{4}{11} \right)^{4/3} N_{\text{eff}} \right)$$

$$\Omega_i = \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_c}$$

- $N_{\text{eff}} = 3.044$ in the standard model, such that today $n_{\text{C}\nu\text{B}} \simeq 110 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\Omega_{\text{C}\nu\text{B}} \simeq \frac{m_\nu}{93h^2 \text{ eV}}$

- Relativistic ν are **free-streaming**: specific impact on CMB at early-times; on structures at late-times.

Cosmology provides strong bounds on ν -physics

- Strongest bounds to date on $\sum m_\nu$ (at 95% CL)

Katrin: < 1.35 eV

Science 2025

Planck 2018 + BAO < 0.12 eV

Planck 1807.06209

Planck 2018 + DESI DR2 < 0.0691 eV

DESI 2503.14738

Planck 2020 + ACT + DESI DR2 < 0.0606 eV

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Planck + ACT + SPT + DESI DR2 < 0.048 eV

SPT 2506.20707

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- Strongest bounds on number of ν -like species (at 68% CL)

Planck 2018 + BAO $N_{\text{eff}} = 2.99 \pm 0.17$

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Planck 2018 + ACT + DESI DR1 $N_{\text{eff}} = 2.86 \pm 0.13$

ACT 2503.14454

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Where are the neutrinos?!

m_ν can affect cosmological distances

- ν can affect the **homogeneous expansion**

$$H(z) \equiv \frac{\dot{a}}{a} = H_0 \sqrt{\Omega_m(1+z)^3 + \Omega_r(1+z)^4 + \Omega_\Lambda + \dots}$$

- Affect distance measurements via SN1a and BAO

$$D_M(z) = \int_0^z \frac{cdz}{H(z)}$$

m_ν can affect probes of matter structuring

CMB weak lensing

Galaxy correlation function (SDSS/BOSS)

Galaxy weak lensing (KiDS / DES)

Galaxy cluster mass function

The Lyman- α forest (MIKE/HIRES)

m_ν suppresses the clustering of matter

$$M_\nu = 1.9 \text{ eV}$$

$$M_\nu = 0 \text{ eV}$$

The density field is “smoother” on small scales

m_ν suppresses the matter power spectrum

For ν 's suppression at $k \geq k_{\text{nr}} \equiv 0.01 \left(\frac{m_\nu}{1\text{eV}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{\Omega_m}{0.3} \right)^{1/2} h\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ and amplitude $\frac{\Delta P}{P} \simeq -8 \frac{\omega_\nu}{\omega_m}$

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ν can affect the cosmic microwave background

A perfect black-body carrying tiny anisotropies $\Delta T/T \sim 10^{-5}$

- The anisotropy pattern is due to an **acoustic wave** propagating in the plasma: **baryon acoustic oscillations**.
- The **CMB power spectra carries information about the plasma** in which the wave propagated.
- Characteristic scale: the **sound horizon** $\theta_s = r_s / D_A(z_*) \equiv \pi / \ell_s \sim 1^\circ$ **a standard ruler to measure distances**

ν can affect the cosmic microwave background

For $\sum m_\nu < 1$ eV, the main effect of neutrinos is to **alter the lensing** in the CMB

$$\sum m_\nu < 0.17 \text{ eV}$$

Planck + SPT + ACT 2506.20707

Naredo-Tuero (VP)++ 2407.13831

The Baryonic Acoustic Oscillation with DESI

- Galaxy catalogues made of **over 5 000 000 objects** with $z \sim 0.1 - 2.1$
- Baryonic acoustic oscillation is the counterparts of what is seen in **CMB anisotropies**

Picture from Etienne Burtin

$$\frac{r_d}{D_M} = \frac{H_0 r_d}{\int_0^z dz \sqrt{(\Omega_m (1+z)^3 + \Omega_\Lambda)}} \quad \Omega_\Lambda = 1 - \Omega_m$$

BAO measurements from DESI

DESI 2503.14738

DESI is in $\sim 3\sigma$ tension with CMB

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- ν mass also means larger Ω_m today: **affects cosmological distances!**

CMB+DESI $\sum m_\nu < 0.048$ eV
SPT 2506.20707

No ν 's is good news?

Craig++ 2405.00836

- When allowing for (effective) $m_\nu < 0$ eV

$$\sum m_{\nu,\text{eff}} = -0.101^{+0.047}_{-0.056} \text{ eV}$$

Elbers++ 2407.10965

DESI 2503.14744 $\sum m_{\nu,\text{eff}}$ [eV]

- Also seen in Frequentist analyses

DESI 2503.14744

Naredo-Tuero (VP)++ 2407.13831

A statistical fluke?

The screenshot shows the Science journal website. At the top, the Science logo is on the left, and navigation links for 'Current Issue', 'First release papers', 'Archive', and 'About' are on the right. A 'Submit manuscript' button is also visible. Below the navigation, a breadcrumb trail reads 'HOME > SCIENCE > VOL. 388, NO. 6743 > DIRECT NEUTRINO-MASS MEASUREMENT BASED ON 259 DAYS OF KATRIN DATA'. The article title is 'Direct neutrino-mass measurement based on 259 days of KATRIN data'. Below the title, the authors are listed: 'KATRIN COLLABORATION, MAY AKER, DOMINIC RATZ, ERIC ARMSTRONG, ARIAN IAN REHRENS, JUSTUS REISENKÖTTER, MATTEO RIASSOMI, BENEDIKT RIEFINGER'. The abstract section is highlighted in light gray and contains the following text: 'That neutrinos carry a nonvanishing rest mass is evidence of physics beyond the Standard Model of elementary particles. Their absolute mass holds relevance in fields from particle physics to cosmology. We report on the search for the effective electron antineutrino mass with the KATRIN experiment. KATRIN performs precision spectroscopy of the tritium β -decay close to the kinematic endpoint. On the basis of the first five measurement campaigns, we derived a best-fit value of $m_\nu^2 = -0.14_{-0.15}^{+0.13} \text{ eV}^2$, resulting in an upper limit of $m_\nu < 0.45 \text{ eV}$ at 90% confidence level. Stemming from 36 million electrons collected in 259 measurement days, a substantial reduction of the background level, and improved systematic uncertainties, this result tightens KATRIN's previous bound by a factor of almost two.'

- Within Katrin, it is attributed to under fluctuations compatible with **statistical fluke**
- There are **two main reasons** driving this preference in CMB data: **fluke + wrong background model ?**

$m_\nu < 0$ is due to a “lensing anomaly” in Planck

- Planck 2018 has an anomalous amount of lensing

$$C_\ell^{\phi\phi} \rightarrow A_L C_\ell^{\phi\phi}, \quad A_L = 1.180 \pm 0.065$$

- This anomaly went down with PR4

$$A_L = 1.039 \pm 0.052$$

- The preference for $m_\nu < 0$ goes away when using a newer version *Planck* data (NPIPE)

m_ν is degenerate with the effect of dark energy

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Summary of neutrino mass bounds

DESI 2503.14744, 2504.18464

- Despite anomalies, it is hard to get rid of the neutrino mass bound from cosmology

Flat Λ CDM (3 deg ν 's)

$$\text{Planck+DESI} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.064 \text{ eV}$$

$$\text{Planck+ ACT +DESI} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.06 \text{ eV}$$

$w_0 w_a$ CDM (3 deg ν 's)

$$\text{Planck+DESI} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.163 \text{ eV}$$

$$\text{Planck+ ACT +DESI} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.152 \text{ eV}$$

$$\text{Planck+ ACT + SN1a} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.117\text{-}0.139 \text{ eV}$$

- Enforcing neutrino mass ordering leads to a preference for NO over IO at 10 : 1

Planck + DESI + NuFIT6.0 (Λ CDM)

$$\text{NO} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.101 \text{ eV} \Rightarrow m_l < 0.023 \text{ eV}$$

$$\text{IO} \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.133 \text{ eV} \Rightarrow m_l < 0.024 \text{ eV}$$

How can we get rid of neutrino mass bounds ?

- 1/ Introduce **new physics in the dark sector (anti-)degenerate** with the background and perturbation effects of neutrinos

- Dynamical dark energy

- Decaying dark matter (into a dark sector)

$$\Omega_{\text{DDM}}^{\text{ini}} \simeq \Omega_{\nu} < \Omega_{\text{cdm}}; \Gamma_{\text{DDM}} \gg H_0$$

Montandon, VP, Rink, Schwetz (in prep)

How can we get rid of neutrino mass bounds ?

Oldengott++ 1901.04352

$$\mathcal{L} = h_{ij} \bar{\nu}_i \nu_j \phi + g_{ij} \bar{\nu}_i \gamma_5 \nu_j \phi + \text{h.c.}$$

- 2/ Introduce new neutrino properties that **alter their phase space distributions**

$$f_\nu(q, T) \neq \frac{1}{\exp(q/T_\nu) + 1}$$

- Neutrino self-scattering

Hannestad++ 1310.5926

- Neutrino annihilations (“neutrino-less universe”)

Beacom++ astro-ph/0404585

- Neutrino decays

Hannestad&Raffelt hep-ph/0509278

- Neutrino long-range interactions

Esteban&Jordi 2101.05804

ν decays could explain no cosmological detection

- Consider a scenario where ν decay at late-times:

$$\nu_i \rightarrow \nu_4 \phi$$

$$\bar{f}_\nu(q, \tau) = \bar{f}_{\text{ini}}(q) e^{-\Gamma_\nu \int_{\tau_{\text{ini}}}^{\tau} \frac{a}{\gamma(a)} d\tau'}$$

- Neutrino decays may **reconcile a detection at Katrin and cosmology bounds** if $\tau_\nu < 8 \times 10^{12} \text{s} (\text{eV}/m_\nu)^{3/2}$
- Detection of non-zero M_ν could lead to **strong constraints on $\tau_\nu^{\text{inv.}} > \tau_u \sim 10^{19} \text{s}$** .

See e.g. Chacko++ hep-ph/0312267, Hannestad&Raffelt hep-ph/0509278, Archidiacono++ 1311.3873, Escudero&Fairbairn 1907.05425, Chen++2203.09075

Current constraints to N_{eff}

- Strongest bounds on number of ν -like species (at 68% CL)

$$\text{Planck 2018} + \text{BAO } N_{\text{eff}} = 2.99 \pm 0.17 \quad \text{Planck 1807.06209}$$

$$\text{Planck 2018} + \text{ACT} + \text{DESI DR1 } N_{\text{eff}} = 2.86 \pm 0.13 \quad \text{ACT 2503.14454}$$

- The bounds have increased mostly because ACT prefers a slightly more scale-invariant spectrum

$$\mathcal{P}(k) = A_s \left(\frac{k}{k_*} \right)^{n_s - 1}$$

$$n_s = 0.9651 \pm 0.0044 \quad \text{Planck 2018}$$

$$n_s = 0.9743 \pm 0.0034 \quad \text{Planck} + \text{ACT}$$

Planck P-ACT P-ACT-LB

ACT 2503.14454

- BBN allows to constrain $N_{\text{eff}} = 2.88 \pm 0.27$ (68% C.L.)

Pitrou++1801.08023

CMB probes exotic ν interaction

$$f(x^\mu, P_\mu) = f_0(\tau, q) [1 + \Psi(\vec{x}, \tau, q, \hat{n})] \quad \Psi(\vec{k}, \hat{n}, q, \tau) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (-i)^l (2l+1) \Psi_l(\vec{k}, q, \tau) P_l(\hat{k} \cdot \hat{n})$$

$$\frac{d\Psi_2}{d\tau} = \frac{qk}{5\epsilon} (2\Psi_1 - 3\Psi_3) - \left(\frac{1}{15} \dot{h} + \frac{2}{5} \dot{\eta} \right) \frac{d \ln f_0}{d \ln q} - a \Gamma_{\text{nfs}} \Psi_2$$

- Exotic self-interaction can **erase free-streaming** and make extra radiation behaves as **perfect fluid**.
- Once interactions are switched on: **γ -perturbations are enhanced / phase is washed-out.**

exotic ν interaction can slightly relax constraints

- Constraints on **interacting dark radiation slightly weaker** than free-streaming species
- ACT strongly impact constraints due to slightly different high- ℓ tilt

ACT 2503.14454

Planck + ACT + DESI

$$\Delta N_{\text{eff}} < 0.076$$

$$N_{\text{IDR}} < 0.134$$

Towards measuring ν properties

DESI

2023

1σ sensitivity to $\sum m_\nu$

0.02-0.03 eV

1σ sensitivity to N_{eff}

0.08-0.13

ESA Euclid

2024

0.011 – 0.02 eV

0.05

LSST

2024

0.015 eV

0.05

CMB-S4

2027

0.015 eV

0.02 – 0.04

© Yvonne Wong

Also SKA, Hera can help in measurement 21cm power spectrum and reionization.

In the future, cosmological probes are expected to detect the neutrino mass even if $M_\nu = 0.06$ eV

However systematics will have to be under control

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Science 2025

Planck+ ACT + SPT + DESI $\sum m_\nu < 0.048 \text{ eV}$ Flat Λ CDM

Planck+ ACT + SN1a $\sum m_\nu < 0.117\text{-}0.139 \text{ eV}$ $w_0 w_a$ CDM

DESI 2504.18464

- Relaxing bounds require exotic dark sector and/or neutrinos
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We are on the verge of interesting discoveries about neutrino in cosmology

Planck

WMAP

ACT

SPT

Thanks for your attention

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The role of the optical depth τ

- The amplitude is correlated with the optical depth to reionization τ

$$C_\ell \propto A_s \exp(-2\tau)$$

- The low- ℓ EE spectrum constrains

$$\tau = 0.0592 \pm 0.0062$$

- Without low- ℓ EE information,

$$\tau = 0.09 \pm 0.012, \quad \sum m_\nu < 0.2 \text{ eV}$$

Planck 2016

Karwal+ 2504.21813

Karwal+ 2504.21813

ν self-interaction can alter CMB bounds

Kreisch++ 1902.00534

- $\mathcal{L} = G_{\text{eff}} \bar{\nu} \nu \bar{\nu} \nu$ Neutrino interacting through (pseudo-) scalar heavy mediator, analogous to Fermi interaction
- There exists two “modes” in *Planck* TT data! *Lancaster++ 1704.06657*

ν self-interaction can alter CMB bounds

Kreisch++ 1902.00534

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- There exists two “modes” in *Planck* TT data! *Lancaster++ 1704.06657*
- **Standard ν with $G_{\text{eff}} = G_{\text{F}}$, $N_{\text{eff}} = 2.99 \pm 0.34$, $\sum m_{\nu} < 0.12$, $H_0 \simeq 67$ km/s/Mpc, eV and $\sigma_8 \simeq 0.83$**
- **Exotic ν with $G_{\text{eff}} = 10^{10} G_{\text{F}}$ (!!)** $N_{\text{eff}} = 4 \pm 0.3$, $\sum m_{\nu} = 0.4 \pm 0.2$, $H_0 \simeq 72$ km/s/Mpc, eV and $\sigma_8 \simeq 0.79 \pm 0.02$
- Can we firmly kill the strongly interacting mode?

It is hard to kill strong self interactions!

- Planck polarization + BAO data **disfavor the strongly interacting mode.**
- New DESI and Planck NPIPE have equal likelihoods between standard model neutrinos and SI interacting ones
- Even ACT DR6 “likes” having one (out of three) SI neutrinos